

Epidemics and Pandemics In Human History - A Review

Research Article

Jothi Priya^{1*}, Lekha², Hannah³

¹ Assistant professor, Department of physiology Saveetha dental college and hospitals, Saveetha Institute of Medical and Technical Sciences. Saveetha University Chennai, India.

² Saveetha dental college and hospitals, Saveetha Institute of Medical and Technical Sciences. Saveetha University Chennai, India.

³ Senior Lecturer Department of Oral and Maxillofacial Pathology and Microbiology, Saveetha dental college and hospitals, Saveetha Institute of Medical and Technical Sciences. Saveetha University.

Abstract

Several accounts of influenza, cholera, dengue, smallpox and several other records of history were able to eradicate some. epidemics are an abnormal occurrence in a society, region of disease, specified health for coupled behavior and other health - related events clearly in surplus are anticipated occurrences. Sudden severe widespread outbreak of disease pre-existing in the community. The study was planned to conduct a literature review collecting sources from databases like google scholar, pubmed etc. The articles were collected between the year 2000-2020. The out come or result of this study are based on the research done by the researchers. The pandemics and epidemics are deadly diseases compared to other diseases. The consequences are very large and the preventive measures to stop are very less. The medical team which is the doctors, researchers, health care workers, etc plays an important role in this kind of situation. Good medical care efficient research made it possible to fight every infection. Luckily we were even able to eradicate a few.

Keywords: Epidemic; Infectiology; Human History; Outbreak; Pandemic.

Introduction

India is the third-world country encountered for a variety of epidemics and pandemics in all time. Several accounts of influenza, cholera, dengue, smallpox and several other records of history were able to eradicate some. Many diseases continue to pose a threat to the community. It is uncommon like a sudden rapid outbreaks occur in India many articles direct cause that to find. Developing countries has malnutrition, lack of sanitation, lack proper public health system [18]. Associated lower respiratory infections cause about 28,000 and 111,500 deaths globally only among children below 5 years [21] Influenza A pandemics have been the cause for millions of deaths during the past several hundred years. The 1918 to 1919 influenza pandemic was the worst pandemic disaster in history [3]. Influenza pandemic killed an estimated 50 million people all around the world , most of them within a

span of just a few months during the fall season of that year [28]. Dr. Park has said that epidemics are an unusual occurrence in a community, region of disease, specific health for related behavior and other health-related events clearly in excess are expected occurrences. Sudden severe widespread outbreak of disease pre-existing in the community. Study by John T. Watson, et all say to analyse the relationship between epidemics and natural disasters to establish that there is a rise in the occurrence of epidemics post-disaster incident which occurred in India may not have not been emphasized [27]. India is concerned that there have only been two significant pandemics in history. While cholera is quite predominant in the 19th century which increases, death tolls every year, then influenza pandemic came in later - early 20th century. The influenza pandemic was short and devastating after a long time. Quite recently we came to know of another flu pandemic which is the H1N1 strain [15]. They examined the early AIDS

*Corresponding Author:

Jothi Priya,

Assistant professor, Department of physiology Saveetha dental college and hospitals, Saveetha Institute of Medical and Technical Sciences. Saveetha University Chennai, India.

Tel: 8778996993

Email Id: jothipriya.sdc@saveetha.com

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epidemic in the United States and India, and specifically investigated the interplay between the general public, federal government, medical community, and patients [11]. Pandemics on the other hand is known as worldwide spread diseases. These global health problems need to be addressed viciously along with proper measures to avoid transmission with other countries. There have been significant number pandemics through out history in many instances. They are very difficult to control because they lack of a proper working global surveillance system [13].

India stood strong through several epidemics and pandemics. Good medical care efficient research made it possible to fight every infection. Luckily we were even able to eradicate a few It has been established through out time and many infectious diseases become widespread due to mere lack sanitation and crowded environment. The tropical climate during the seasonal rains -in India yet another important factor contributing several vector borne infections outbreaks may pass many more and come. Though it has been difficult to compile all the epidemics pandemics due to lack of sufficient and available data and errors in data preservation of sincere efforts including most important which are notable ones [24]. On the first wave of cholera outburst, the plan was brought by health officials. New lazarettos were scheme at western ports, and a substantial structure was established near Bordeaux, France [26]. Many Epidemics and Pandemics in human history were noted in the past centuries. Cure has not been found till now for some of these fatal diseases. The current study has compared all the epidemic and pandemic outbreak of the past and present century. The aim of this study is to review all epidemics and pandemics.

Our institution has conducted many clinical trials and survey topics which inspired us also to do a survey [7, 4, 5, 22, 9]. There were also some review topic done by our university about obesity in relation to infertility etc [20, 6, 14, 2, 23, 25]. There are some study done by our university on pathogenesis and Novel drug for treatment etc [19, 17, 1, 16]. Now the institution is focussing on epidemiological surveys.

Materials and Methods

The study was planned to conduct a literature review collecting sources from databases like googlescholar, pubmed etc. The articles were collected between the year 2000-2020. The outcome or result of this study are based on the research done by the researchers. Each article is reviewed thoroughly and main points are highlighted in this study The outcome is to report the status of the pandemic outbreak of Covid-19 and similar outbreaks in the past century. The collected data will be analysed using appropriate statistical tools.

Discussion

Epidemics and Pandemics

From TABLE 1 we can see that there is a background study done for each review article explaining the key point and selection of appropriate points suitable for our study. The TABLE 1 gives an overview of articles we reviewed in one or two lines. we can see that the article by Rice et al was These articles explain pandemics briefly and also include important points and information where-

as the article done by Watson et al and Swetha et al was strong and many good aspects were seen and in article done by Ramamurthy et al and article done by Cunha they are not as much of information as seen in the other article but the they have tried to explain about epidemics and pandemics as simple as possible for a better understanding where as the articles done by Pike et al, article by Martin et al, article done by Mehta et al and article by Worobey et al was also like Rice et al, These articles explain epidemics and pandemics briefly and also include important aspects. The article By Huremovie and an article by Saunders-Hastings et al are verified as strong. These articles give a lot of information on both epidemics and pandemics.

The pandemics and epidemics are deadly diseases compared to other diseases. The consequence are very large and the preventive measures to stop is very less The medical team which is the doctors, researchers, health care workers, etc plays an important role in this kind of situation and try their best to help to cure the pandemic or atleast prevent the disease from spreading more. There are various cases in the history of pandemics such as Awal influenza, cholera, Ebola, Plague, Yellow fever, Meningitis, 'MERS, Influenza, Zika; Rift Valley Fever, Lassa fever, leptospirosis Covid 19, SARS etc.

Pandemics Across Globe

Globally HIV pandemic outbreak of pathogens like SARS, H5N, influenza virells, Hant., influenza pandemics have consequences still which is still to be determined and demonstrate continued vulnerability to emerging infectious disease [24] SARS (CoronaVirus) started in China has affected fewer than 10,000 individuals in China, Hongkong, also in other countries and a total of 251 cases in Canada [8]. Escaping pandemic entirely may not be the most advantageous strategy because it only leaves everyone susceptible to infection later [12]. The term epidemic existed in 430 BC. The Greek word epidemios means constructed ano demos means "The country" before taking the connotation" the people in Classical Greek" [10]. The strongest and most consistent malnutrition increases the risk of death like acute respiratory infection [11]. During risk outbreak of natural disasters are low, pareticuleste disaster does not result substantial population displacement [27] cholera global health problems are several thousand cases death that occur each year [13].

The number of articles collected are less compared to other review and article selection biases. For future study we wanted to do a survey based research to check the awareness, knowledge, attitude and practice towards epidemics and pandemics in human history.

Conclusion

This review was done based on many objectives like response, understanding, quality of article etc. This review was done to know about epidemics and pandemics in human history. Many types of epidemics and pandemics were discussed in detail in this review study. This study also explains about some preventive measures for epidemics and pandemics. By this study we can prevent mistakes from the past while handling these epidemics and pandemics. Even though the infections cannot be stopped spreading that easily, the government officials, doctors and other health care

Table 1. Summary table.

S.NO	TITLE	AUTHOR	JOURNAL	BACKGROUND
1	Malnutrition as an underlying cause of childhood deaths associated with infectious diseases in developing countries.	Rice AL, Sacco L, Hyder A, Black RE.	Bull World Health Organ.	Many diseases continue to pose a threat to the community. It is uncommon like a sudden rapid outbreaks occur in India many articles direct cause that to find .developing countries has malnutrition, lack of sanitation, lack proper public health system.
2	Reviewing the History of Pandemic Influenza: Understanding Patterns of Emergence and Transmission.	Saunders-Hastings PR, Krewski D.	Pathogens	The relationship between epidemics -and natural disasters to establishes that there is a rise in the occurrence of epidemics post-disaster incident which occurred in India may not be not been emphasized
3	Influenza: historical aspects of epidemics and pandemics.	Cunha BA.	Infect Dis Clin North Am	The influenza pandemic was short and devastating after a long time . Quite recently we came to know another flu pandemic which is H1N1 strain
4	The origins of the great pandemic,	Worobey M, Cox J, Gill D.	Evolution, Medicine, and Public Health	There have been significant number pandemics throughout history in many instances. They are very difficult to control because they lack of a proper working global surveillance system
5	Epidemics after natural disasters.	Watson JT, Gayer M, Connolly MA.	Emerg Infect Dis	Good medical care - efficient researches made it possible to fight every infection luckily we were even able to eradicate few It has been established throughout time and many infectious diseases become widespread due to mere lack sanitation and crowded environment
6	Cholera outbreaks in India.	Ramamurthy T, Sharma NC.	Curr Top MicrobiolImmunol	SARS (CoronaVirus) started in China has affected fewer than 10,000 individuals in China, Hongkong.
7	Addressing Future Epidemics: Historical Human Rights Lessons from the AIDS Pandemic.	Mehta A, Quinn TC.	Pathog Immun.	The teren epidemic existed in 430 BC. The Greek word epidemios means constructed ano demos means “The country” before taking the connotation “ the people in Classical Greek
8	The Origin and Prevention of Pandemics	Pike BL, Saylor KE, Fair JN, LeBreton M, Tamoufe U, Djoko CF, et al.	Infectious Diseases	Escaping pandemic entirely may not be the most advantageous strategy because it only leaves everyone susceptible to infection later
9	Epidemics and Pandemics in India throughout History: A Review Article.	Swetha G, Eashwar VM, Gopalakrishnan S.	Indian Journal of Public Health Research & Development.	J. Associated lower respiratory infections cause about 28,000 and 111,500 deaths globally only among children below 5 years.
10	Lessons from the History of Quarantine, from Plague to Influenza A	Tognotti E.	Emerging Infectious Diseases.	The 1918 to 1919 influenza pandemic was the worst pandemic disaster in history
11	Brief History of Pandemics (Pandemics Throughout History)	Huremović D.	Psychiatry of Pandemics	Specifically investigated the interplay between the general public, federal government, medical community, and patients
12	Pandemic influenza: studying the lessons of history.	Morse SS.	ProcNatlAcad-Sci U S A.	Escaping pandemic entirely may not be the most advantageous strategy because it only leaves everyone susceptible to infection later
13	2,500-year Evolution of the Term Epidemic	Martin PMV, Martin-Granel E.	Emerging Infectious Diseases	Influenza pandemic killed an estimated 50 million people all around the world, most of them within a span of just a few months during the fall season of that year

workers try their best to stop the spread of the disease. This study can be useful for future studies when a same type of new epidemics or pandemics occurs.

Authors Contribution

Data collection, collection of reviews, drafting manuscript was done by Lekha. D. Structuring study design, revising manuscript,

final approval of manuscript was done by JothiPriya. A . Drafting and revising manuscript was done by Hannah. R.

Conflict Of Interest - NIL

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